

1th. International Conference on Design in Civil Engineering,
Architecture and Urban Planning / 29 February 2024

Venue: Azerbaijan - Baku

Optimizing the Parameters of the Tuned Mass Damper Inerter to Reduce the Park-Ang Damage Index

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Abstract

This paper explores the practical benefits of a Tuned Mass Damper Inerter (TMDI) over the classic Tuned Mass Damper (TMD). The focus is demonstrating that TMDI has a better damage index reduction capability due to its inertial amplifying effect. Moreover, the study also investigates the possibility of enhancing the inertial property of TMDI to improve its performance without adding mass to the damper. A 9-story building frame is considered for the nonlinear dynamic analysis. TMDI and TMD are designed using the centralized plasticity model and optimized through meta-heuristic algorithms, including the Harris hawk algorithm. The study results indicate that TMDI shows higher efficiency and effectiveness in reducing the damage index than TMD due to its inertial amplifier effect.

Keywords: Tuned Mass Damper Inerter, Park-Ang Damage Index, Meta-heuristic Algorithm, Nonlinear Dynamic Analysis

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1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, the Tuned Mass Damper (TMD) has been widely regarded as a viable option for reducing structural vibrations resulting from seismic activity. Several studies have indicated that TMD can effectively safeguard structural systems against damage caused by earthquake vibrations. The research conducted by Den Hartog and Ormondroyd played a significant role in this regard [1]. Several methods have been devised to optimize the design of TMD for mitigating the vibrations induced by seismic events [2]. One frequently used approach to design TMD is based on the fixed point theory [3]. The research presented a precise closed solution for optimal adjustment of TMD parameters based on the fixed point theory [4]. The first hypothesis assumed TMD to be a combination of a mass, spring, and viscous damper attached to the structure, which controlled the vibrations. The larger the mass of the TMD attached, the better the performance of the structure under vibration control, considering the architectural and structural constraints.

Additionally, several researchers have suggested using TMD with a large mass attached to the top or last few stories, along with seismic separators [5-8]. In studies related to TMD, finding the optimal parameters for TMD (mass, stiffness, and damping) and determining the optimal positioning for TMD connection to the structure are crucial issues [9-14]. In recent years, lightweight TMDs that offer the same or even better performance than classic TMDs have been developed. These systems utilize the mass or inertial amplifier effect, first proposed by Smith in 2002 and known as the inerter [15]. Initially designed for car suspension systems, the inerter can generate a resistance force proportional to the relative acceleration of its terminals, equivalent to twice the apparent mass. This key feature makes the inerter a lower mass alternative to classic TMDs, known as the inertial constant or inerter. Several inerter devices are currently available [16-19].

Richiedei *et al.* [20] conducted a study in which they expanded the function of TMD (tuned mass damper) by introducing an antiresonance approach in response to harmonic base stimulation. Numerical examples were used to compare different aspects and study antiresonance properties, and the study presented a possible orientation for future studies with an antiresonance approach. In another study, Chatziathanasiou *et al.* [21] introduced a semi-active TMD that improves its efficiency and is designed to perform well in a short frequency range. The attenuator comprises a piezoelectric device connected to an electrical circuit, providing multidimensional vibration control to the designer making it easier to adjust. The presented results indicate that the introduced system can effectively reduce the dynamic response of the penalty.

Due to the novelty of inerter device-based TMD (tuned mass damper) systems and related design issues for controlling earthquake vibrations, extensive research has not been conducted on this topic. However, studies have been conducted on VMD (viscous mass dampers), TVMD (viscous tuned mass dampers), TID (tuned inerter dampers), and inerter-based dynamic vibration absorbers, which have developed design methods based on the use of

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frequency response functions [22-24]. Marian and Giaralis proposed TMDI (tuned mass damper inerter), which uses a random input for optimal design by minimizing the response quantity and extracting the analytical closed-form solutions [25]. Brzeski *et al.* studied using an inerter in a tuned mass damper and considered the possibility of changing the inertia in the inerter device [26, 27]. Furthermore, studies on the configuration of the inerter and dampers under seismic excitations have been reviewed, and the effectiveness of the inerter on the structure's response has been evaluated [22, 23, 26, 28]. Studies have been conducted to compare the performance of TMD (tuned mass damper) and TMDI (tuned mass damper inerter) in high-rise structures under seismic excitations. Meta-innovative algorithms have been used to optimize the systems' parameters, aiming to reduce roof displacement, acceleration, and average square displacement. The results indicate that the degree of inertia significantly reduces seismic responses [29]. In another study, the TMDI parameters were optimized to control the displacement of the structure under seismic stimuli close to the fault. Three structures were used in modeling, and seismic motions containing a velocity pulse were predominant. The numerical results clearly show that proper optimization effectively controls the seismic response of the structure under certain conditions [30, 31].

During the modeling and analysis of control systems, it is evident that optimal design of these systems is required for proper conclusions. In recent decades, there has been a surge in the popularity of nature-inspired meta-innovative algorithms. The Harris Hawk optimization (HHO) algorithm is one such algorithm that is inspired by the behavioral patterns of Harris hawks in nature. It is a clever and powerful strategy that can advance the chase pattern based on dynamic nature and set scenarios. The HHO algorithm's problem-solving power has emerged in the engineering world, solving 29 different issues, and statistical results have shown that it is highly effective compared to other meta-heuristic algorithms. In the optimization process of a study, the HHO algorithm was used, which utilizes power in solving the optimization problem [32].

The present study aimed to optimize the parameters of the Tuned Mass Damper Inerter (TMDI) system through meta-heuristic algorithms to minimize the Park-Ang damage index in structural stories and the whole structure. The optimization process employed the Harris hawks algorithm, which exhibited superior performance compared to other populations in the initial population. Nonlinear dynamic analysis was used to analyze the structure, and an artificial earthquake with an acceleration of 0.8 *g* was used to stimulate the structure's base. The results demonstrated the superiority of the TMDI and TMD parameters with the Harris hawk algorithm in minimizing the Park-Ang damage index in the structural stories and the whole structure TMDI performance over the TMD system. The TMDI system, utilizing the inertial property of inerter devices, demonstrated exemplary performance in minimizing the Park-Ang damage index, reducing the total structure damage index by 35%. The study findings indicate that the introduced system, utilizing the inertial property of inerter devices, offers higher efficiency in minimizing the Park-Ang damage index in the structural stories and the damage index in the whole structure compared to conventional TMD systems. Notably, high mass ratios should be used to perform the TMD system properly. However, with a mass ratio of

about 0.01%, the introduced system demonstrated higher efficiency than the TMD system with the same mass ratio. These findings provide a novel perspective on systems that require high mass ratios.

2. System with TMDI

Smith [15] introduced the concept of inerter devices. The ideal inerter is a linear device with two terminals and very low mass. The resistance forces F of the inerter are proportional to the relative acceleration between its two freely moving ends. The resistance force between the two terminals of the inerter device can be expressed as follows:

$$F = b(\ddot{u}_1 + \ddot{u}_2) \quad (1)$$

Where \ddot{u}_1 and \ddot{u}_2 are the accelerations at the beginning and end of the two inerter terminals, which can be seen in Figure 1. In Equation (2), the constant b is called proportionality or so-called inertia and has a unit of mass. The important point is that the inert behavior can double or more than the physical mass of the attenuator. This behavior has been confirmed by experiments with several prototype inert devices to convert transient kinetic energy into rotational kinetic energy. The constant relation of proportion or inertia can be explained as follows:

$$b = m_f \frac{\gamma_f^2}{\gamma_{pr}^2} \left(\prod_{q=1}^n \frac{r_q^2}{pr_q^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where m_f and γ_f are the mass and radius of the flywheel, respectively. γ_{pr} The radius of rotation of the flywheel pinion and $\frac{r_q}{pr_q}$ is the ratio of the gear in phase q to the n phase in the system. In the meantime, it is clear that inertia can be created many times larger by changing the ratios of the gears and producing a mass greater than the mass attached to the system.

Figure 1- Schematic representation of inerter device [33]

In this sense, the ideal inerter device can be introduced as an inertial amplifier device because by connecting each of the terminals, the device acts as an inertia device. These inertial properties have been considered in this study by the Tuned Mass Damper Inerter. They have been used to increase the control of the vibrations of the classical damper. The proposed location of TMDI in multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) structures with seismically excited shear frames is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows a classic TMD on the top story of a structure with mass m_T connected to the structure by a spring with linear stiffness k_T . The TMD mass is connected to the story below the damper by an inerter device with b inertia. The equations of motion of the multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) system under $\ddot{x}_g(t)$ seismic acceleration are expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{x}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{x}(t) + \mathbf{K}x(t) = -\mathbf{M}\iota\ddot{x}_g(t). \quad (3)$$

Where ι is a unit vector with length $(n+1)$ and \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{K} , and x are the matrix of mass, damping, stiffness, and displacement vector, respectively. The important point in TMDI is that removing the viscous damper will change the value of the \mathbf{C} matrix. The above expressions are generally expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{S,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & m_{S,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & m_{S,i} & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & (m_{S,n-1} + b) & 0 & -b \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & m_{S,n} & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & -b & 0 & m_T + b \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

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$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} (c_{S,1} + c_{S,2}) & -c_{S,2} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -c_{S,2} & (c_{S,2} + c_{S,i}) & -c_{S,i} & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & -c_{S,i} & (c_{S,i} + c_{S,n-1}) & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & (c_{S,n} + c_T) & -c_T \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & -c_T & c_T \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} (k_{S,1} + k_{S,2}) & -k_{S,2} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -k_{S,2} & (k_{S,2} + k_{S,i}) & -k_{S,i} & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & -k_{S,i} & (k_{S,i} + k_{S,n-1}) & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & (k_{S,n} + k_T) & -k_T \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & -k_T & k_T \end{bmatrix},$$

$$x(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_i \\ x_{n-1} \\ \vdots \\ x_n \\ x_T \end{bmatrix}$$

In Equation (4) $m_{S,i}$, $k_{S,i}$ and $c_{S,i}$, respectively, the mass, stiffness, and damping of the stories are such that $i = (i=1,2,\dots,n)$ and m_T , k_T and c_T are the mass, stiffness, and damping of TMDI and b , respectively, and the inertia coefficient of the inerter device, as shown in Figure 2. In addition, x_i is the displacement rate of the stories such that $i = (i=1,2,\dots,n)$ and x_T is the displacement rate of the TMDI mass if the inerter is connected to the lower story.

Figure 2- A multi-degree of freedom (MDOF) structure with a shear frame with TMDI

An important point here is that if the position $b = 0$ is placed in equation (4), the response of a multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) structure with a shear frame with a classical TMD will be obtained under earthquake acceleration. In this case, the amount of inertia is equal to zero, which will have no effect on the results. The recent location for TMDI has been chosen to be the most efficient for controlling the vibrations of a structure under an earthquake in the first vibration or mode. The addition of an inerter device removes the structural mass matrix from the diagonal, but the overall structural response remains linear, and from a scientific point of view, the same computational methods used in TMD can be applied in the same way in TMDI. TMDI frequency ratios can be defined as follows:

$$\omega_{TMDI} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{k_T}{m_T + b}}}{\omega_s}, \quad \zeta_{TMDI} = \frac{c_T}{2(m_T + b)\omega_T}. \quad (5)$$

In the above Equation ω_s is the natural frequency of the structure. The design of TMDI has been done in such a way that with the appropriate amount of damper mass and inertia, the amount of damage index under artificial earthquake acceleration reaches its minimum level.

3. Damage Index

In the process of evaluating the performance of the structure, the analysis of the damage to the structure is one of the main steps that lead to the calculation of the damage to the structure. Researchers in recent decades have introduced various types of damage indexes. The damage index considered in this study is based on wasted energy and ductility needs, which, for example, is a Park-Ang damage index, an index that is a linear sum of the maximum amount of deformation and energy wasted [34].

3.1 Park-Ang Damage Index

The modified Park-Ang damage index was used to assess the damage caused by the analysis performed in this study. The Park-Ang damage index is expressed as follows:

$$DI_{PA} = \frac{\delta_m}{\delta_u} + \frac{\beta}{Q_y \delta_u} \int dE \quad (6)$$

Where δ_m deformation of the member under earthquake acceleration, δ_u final deformation of the member proposed by the experimental method of 0.025 for steel structures. Q_y yield stress and E the amount of energy lost. The Park-Ang damage index has been modified by Kunnath *et al.* Based on the rotation of members as follows, which is the basis for damage assessment in this study [35]:

$$DI_{PA} = \frac{\theta_m - \theta_y}{\theta_u - \theta_y} + \frac{\beta}{M_y \theta_u} \int dE \quad (7)$$

Where θ_m is the maximum spin rate, θ_u is the final rotation capacity, θ_y is the yield rotation, and M_y is the yield moment. Also, the damage index in the whole structure is expressed as follows:

$$DI_{Storey} = \sum (\lambda_i)_{component} (DI_i)_{component} ; \quad (\lambda_i)_{component} = \left(\frac{E_{h_i}}{\sum E_{h_i}} \right)_{component} \quad (8)$$

$$DI_{Overall} = \sum (\lambda_i)_{Storey} (DI_i)_{Storey} ; \quad (\lambda_i)_{Storey} = \left(\frac{E_{h_i}}{\sum E_{h_i}} \right)_{Storey} \quad (9)$$

Where λ_i and E_{h_i} represent the energy weighting factors and cumulative absorbed energy by the component or story “*i*”, respectively [36].

Table 1- Range of Park-Ang damage index against seismic damage [37]

Range of DI_{PA}	Damage description
$DI_{PA} < 0.1$	No damage or localized minor cracking
$0.1 \leq DI_{PA} < 0.25$	Minor damage – minor cracking throughout
$0.25 \leq DI_{PA} < 0.4$	Moderate damage - severe cracking and localized spalling
$0.4 \leq DI_{PA} < 1$	Severe damage - crushing of concrete and exposure of reinforcing bars
$DI_{PA} \geq 1$	Collapse

4. Optimal Design of Parameters

4.1 Optimal Design of TMDI System

The optimization process in TMDI is described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Find:} & \quad m_T, k_T, c_T, F \\
 \text{Minimize:} & \quad DI_{PA}(m_T, k_T, c_T, F) \\
 & \quad m_T^{\min} \leq m_T \leq m_T^{\max} \\
 & \quad k_T^{\min} \leq k_T \leq k_T^{\max} \\
 & \quad c_T^{\min} \leq c_T \leq c_T^{\max} \\
 \text{Subjected to:} & \quad F^{\min} \leq F \leq F^{\max} \\
 & \quad \max(|X_T(t) - X_{Roof}(t)|) \leq St_{\max} \\
 & \quad DI_{PA}^{story} \leq 0.3
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Where m_T^{\min} and m_T^{\max} express the upper and lower limits of TMDI mass, respectively. Also, k_T^{\min} and k_T^{\max} are the upper and lower limits of nonlinear TMDI stiffness, respectively, and c_T^{\min} and c_T^{\max} are the upper and lower limits of TMDI damping, and finally F^{\min} , and F^{\max} are the upper and lower limits of the amount of inertial force in the inerter device connected to the mass and story in the system. The stroke capacity of the system and the class damage index are considered as Equation (10).

4.2 Optimal Design of TMD System

The optimization process in TMD is described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Find:} & \quad m_T, k_T, c_T \\
 \text{Minimize:} & \quad DI_{PA}(m_T, k_T, c_T) \\
 & \quad m_T^{\min} \leq m_T \leq m_T^{\max} \\
 & \quad k_T^{\min} \leq k_T \leq k_T^{\max} \\
 \text{Subjected to:} & \quad c_T^{\min} \leq c_T \leq c_T^{\max} \\
 & \quad \max(|X_T(t) - X_{Roof}(t)|) \leq St_{\max} \\
 & \quad DI_{PA}^{story} \leq 0.3
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Where m_T^{\min} and m_T^{\max} express the upper and lower limits of TMD mass, respectively. Also, k_T^{\min} and k_T^{\max} are the upper and lower limits of nonlinear TMD stiffness, respectively, and c_T^{\min} and c_T^{\max} are the upper and lower limits of TMD damping, respectively, and the stroke capacity of the system and the class damage index are considered as Equation (11).

Table 2- The upper and lower limits of the parameters considered in the optimization

Inertance ratio [38]	Mass ratio [38]	Damping ratio [38]	Frequency ratio [39]
$0.0 \leq \beta \leq 1.0$	$0.002 \leq \mu \leq 0.02$	$0.05 \leq \zeta \leq 2.5$	$0.01 \leq \nu \leq 10.0$

The optimization parameters listed in Table 2 are generally expressed as follows:

$$\nu = \frac{\omega_0}{\omega_s} \quad \zeta = \frac{c_0}{2m_0\omega_0} \quad \mu = \frac{m_0}{m_s} \quad \beta = \frac{b}{m_s} \tag{12}$$

Where ω_0 , c_0 , m_0 represent the frequency, damping, and mass of the damper, respectively, and ω_s and m_s are the frequency and mass of the main structure. ν , ζ , μ and β are also frequency ratio, damping ratio, mass ratio, and inertia force ratio, respectively.

5. Meta-Heuristic Algorithms

5.1 Harris Hawk Optimization Algorithm (HHO)

This algorithm is inspired by the interactive and participatory behavior of a type of falcon in nature called the Harris Falcon. In order to hunt, these falcons form a kind of interaction and social behavior with each other so that they can surprise and hunt the prey.

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Now, with the idea of hunting Harris hawk, the HHO algorithm has been formulated and has good power in solving optimization problems [32]. In the optimization process with the HHO algorithm, the number of search factors and the number of iterations per search factor is 30, which will eventually lead to a different number of cycles for optimization.

Table 3- Limits of optimal design variables used in TMDI

The parameters of the TMDI	Lower bound	Upper bound
$m_T (N \cdot \text{sec}^2 / m)$	15000	150000
$k_T (N / m)$	3600	773000
$c_T (N \cdot \text{sec} / m)$	3400	367500
$F(N)$	0	7500000

Table 4- Limits of optimal design variables used in TMD

The parameters of the TMD	Lower bound	Upper bound
$m_T (N \cdot \text{sec}^2 / m)$	15000	150000
$k_T (N / m)$	3600	773000
$c_T (N \cdot \text{sec} / m)$	3400	367500

6. Modeling of 9-story Steel Bending Frame

The structure of the 9-story bending frame with five openings is considered; the height of the ground story is 5.49 meters, and the height of the other stories is 3.96. The structural information is described in detail in the reference [40]. The total mass of the structure is 9.00×10^6 kg, and the length of the frame opening is equal to 9.15 meters. The main natural frequency of the structure in the first three modes is equal to 2.27, 0.85, and 0.49 seconds, respectively. The main damping ratio of the structure is assumed to be 2%, and the yield stress in columns is 345 MPa and in beams is 248 MPa.

In the modeling of this structure, a centralized plasticity model is performed in OpenSees software, and at the junction of the beam to the column, a nonlinear spring with zero length is attached to the element, which represents the centralized plasticity model (see Figure 6). In modeling beams and columns, elastic materials have been used, and to simulate the

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behavior of two-line hysteresis of springs, the Modified Ibarra-Medina-Krawinkler model has been used; the behavior of this model can be seen in Figure 3. In modeling the mentioned bending frame, to model the three-dimensional behavior of the structure in the two-dimensional plane, the elements of the lining columns are used to apply this function well in the structure. It should be noted that the lining columns will not have any effect on the main behavior of the structure and are intended only for applying three-dimensional plan loads on a two-dimensional plane.

Figure 3- A 9-story steel bending frame

Figure 4- (a) View of the connection spring (b) How to model the spring in the connection spring [41]

Figure 5- The hysteretic curve for the modified IMK behavioral decline model [42]

7. Artificial Earthquake Modeling

In this study, an artificial earthquake was used to stimulate the foundation of the structure, which is calculated as follows:

$$S_{Kanai-Tajimi}(\omega) = S_0 \left[\frac{\omega_g^4 + (2 \times \omega_g \times \xi_g \times \omega)^2}{(\omega^2 - \omega_g^2)^2 + (2 \times \omega_g \times \xi_g \times \omega)^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$S_0 = \frac{0.03 \times \xi_g}{\pi \times \omega_g \times (4 \times \xi_g^2 + 1)}$$

Where S_0 intensity is a function of power spectral density (PSDF) [43, 44] and also ω_g soil frequency and ξ_g indicate soil damping, the soil frequency is assumed to be 25.13 radians per second, and the soil damping is assumed to be 0.8 [45]. Also, in this study, PGA = 0.8 is considered that Figure 8 accelerates the time history and can be seen in Table 5 of the properties of artificial earthquakes.

Figure 6- Accelerate the time history of artificial earthquakes

Table 5- Properties of artificial earthquakes

Earthquake	PGA (m/sec^2)	PGA/PGV ($g.sec/m$)	Strong ground motion duration (sec)	Predominant period (sec)	Total time duration (sec)	Arias Intensity (m/sec)
Artificial earthquake	8.024	0.0022	18	0.22	19.98	1499.0045

Therefore, the 9-story bending frame under an artificial earthquake is analyzed, and the optimal parameters of TMDI and TMD are designed to minimize the Park-Ang damage index.

8. Results

This section focuses on the effects of an artificial earthquake on the 9-story bending frame. The HHO algorithm is used to calculate the optimal values of the parameters mentioned in TMDI and TMD. The results indicate that TMDI is successful in reducing the Park-Ang damage index. Twenty initial population groups were utilized in the optimization process, and the best initial population was eventually chosen. The optimization of two dampers used the same selected population as the algorithm starts optimizing from the same points, and the results are not affected by different starting points. Table 6 shows the amount of damage index in the structure with uncontrolled and controlled modes.

Table 6- Structural response in uncontrolled mode and controlled in optimal mode parameters

System	Roof disp. (m)	Roof accel. (m/sec ²)	Global drift ratio	Park-Ang damage index	Reduction			
					Percentage(%)			
					Roof disp. (m)	Roof accel. (m/sec ²)	Global drift ratio	Park-Ang damage index
Uncontrol	0.735	11.82	0.0075	0.452				
Controlled by TMD	0.739	11.65	0.0073	0.439	-0.54	1.49	2.27	4.99
Controlled by TMDI	0.708	10.19	0.0085	0.293	3.61	13.80	-12.34	35.92

According to the results, TMDI performs exceptionally well in reducing the Park-Ang damage index, with a decrease of 35% in the optimal case. Additionally, it is observed that TMDI has a significant decreasing trend in roof acceleration. However, it is also noted that TMDI increases the overall drift of the structure, but the amount of increase is within the allowable drift range of the structure (0.025). On the other hand, TMD increases roof displacement and has a positive impact on reducing the Park-Ang damage index. Figure 7 shows the amount of damage index in the structure with uncontrolled and controlled modes.

Figure 7- Response of story damage index in optimal condition

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According to the results, TMDI performs exceptionally well in reducing the story drift ratio, with a decrease of 58% in the optimal case. Table 7 shows the story drift ratio in the structure with uncontrolled and controlled modes.

Table 7- Drift ratio of the structural story in optimal condition

System	Story drift ratio								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Uncontrol	0.0439	0.0424	0.0342	0.0213	0.0113	0.0137	0.0127	0.0140	0.0131
Controlled by TMD	0.0430	0.0418	0.0213	0.0340	0.0107	0.0130	0.0124	0.0136	0.0121
Controlled by TMDI	0.0194	0.0234	0.0238	0.0270	0.0300	0.0277	0.0213	0.0159	0.0109

In this section, it can be concluded that TMDI in the lower and upper stories of the structure significantly reduces the story drift, but in contrast to the middle story drift ratio increases. Table 8 shows the number of Optimal values of parameters obtained under artificial earthquake with the HHO algorithm.

Table 8- Optimal values of parameters obtained under artificial earthquake with HHO algorithm

System	k_T	c_T	m_T	ν	ζ	μ	β	Stroke
TMD	7.8462×10^4	9.3542×10^4	7.0991×10^5	1.3251	0.1982	0.0105	-	0.4014
TMDI	7.8462×10^4	9.3542×10^4	7.0991×10^5	1.3251	0.1982	0.0105	0.5018	0.3373

According to the table, if the TMDI system has a lower mass ratio and stroke ratio, it can decrease the Park-Ang damage index and significantly reduce the story drift ratio.

9. Conclusion

The present study introduces the Tuned Mass Damper Inerter (TMDI) system and evaluates its performance against the conventional Tuned Mass Damper (TMD) system. The primary objective of the study is to enhance the seismic performance of structures by minimizing the Park-Ang damage index through the calculation of optimal parameters for TMDI and TMD systems. In this regard, a 9-story bending frame was nonlinearly modeled using OpenSees software, taking into account the connection spring and the centralized plasticity model. The IMK model was utilized to simulate the nonlinear behavior of the

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structure. The MATLAB and OpenSees software were linked in the parameter optimization cycle using the HHO algorithm with different numbers of repetitions but the same population size. The optimization process resulted in identifying optimal parameter values that minimize the Park-Ang damage index. The numerical results obtained from the study demonstrate that the TMDI system outperforms other systems and reduces the structural damage index to 35%, which is remarkably high. Furthermore, the TMDI system effectively reduces the damage index of the lower stories, which is one of the primary reasons for structural collapse. The TMDI system also provides a more practical operating mechanism than other control systems. Overall, the TMDI system has the potential to minimize roof displacement, roof acceleration, and the Park-Ang damage index on stories and the entire structure. The numerical results obtained from this study suggest that the TMDI system could improve the seismic performance of structures.

10. Acknowledgments

The authors thank the Vocational Boy's College of Shahrekord for their spiritual support.

11. Funding

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

12. Conflict of Interests

The authors confirm that there is no conflict of interest.

13. Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets used and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

14. Competing Interests

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The authors confirm that there is no conflict of interest.

15. Authors' Contributions

Mohammad Alibabaei Shahraki: Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Amirhossein Hosseini Chaleshtori:** Investigation, Methodology, Conceptualization

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